

A Study on the Effects of Flood 2018 on Public Education with Special Reference to Ernakulam District

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Abstract

Natural calamities are dangerous and flood could be considered the most devastating among all other natural calamities. Kerala, which was on the rise of development in various sectors was hit adversely by the flood and was regarded as "worst flood of the century". Ernakulam being the hub of Kerala couldn't escape from the treacherous event. The effect was massive that both the mental and physical condition of the people especially the children and old age groups were hit hard and the recovery could happen only with the help of intense support from the interested groups including the government. Among the areas, Aluva and Paravur was stricken down due to flood. This paper examines the effect of flood on education and the mitigation measures that were used by the schools during floods in same area. Primary data will be collected using questionnaires and secondary sources includes newspaper articles, e- literatures on the same.

Keywords: Natural Calamities, Flood, Effect on Education, Mitigation Measures

Introduction

Natural calamities are dangerous and flood could be considered the most devastating among all other natural calamities. Kerala, which was on the rise of development in various sectors was hit adversely by the flood and was regarded as "worst flood of the century". Ernakulam being the hub of Kerala couldn't escape from the treacherous event. The effect was massive that both the mental and physical condition of the people were hit hard and the recovery could happen only with the help of intense support from the interested groups including the government. Education sector is one among which was stricken hard due to flood. The public education was affected and the after effects of the flood took weeks to overcome. Among the areas, Paravur and Aluva were stricken down due to flood. The last worst hit flood happened back in 1924 when a huge mountain (karinthiri mala) and a road to munnar was washed off due to flood.

The World Education Forum's Dakar Framework for Action: Education for All (EFA) (UNESCO, 2000) opined that natural calamities are hindrance in meeting the goal of Education for All. This has to be addressed with intensive national and international support. The flood destroyed many educational institutions and various school had to build from fresh. This gap in instruction and time consuming process may affect the quality of education. When alternative locations are not possible, many students will be denied schooling which ultimately leads to dropout; thus putting an end to the dream of getting education. Another effect of flood is that since their way has either been washed off or destroyed completely, students find it difficult to go

to schools. Even if all these circumstances are crossed by, the parents might feel insecure to send their wards to school due to the fear of collapse of building.

Opportunity cost of education is too high for the poor and so retaining students at school may not be always possible. Another factor is that the qualified teachers may find difficulty in getting placed in schools that are affected due to flood which affects adversely the enrolment and overall performance of the students including quality of education.

Objectives

- To study the effect of flood on education in Ernakulam district
- To study the mitigation measures that were used by the schools during floods in study area

Literature Review

Disaster slow down and hinders the progress towards the achievements of Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) (UN, 2001). Disaster mostly hit the communities, who often fail to send their children to school

More recently, several initiatives have worked to facilitate children's active participation and agency in efforts to prevent, prepare for, cope with and adapt to climate change and when extreme events will come suddenly. Such initiatives cover curriculum development in schools, teacher training, knowledge transferring through a range of media and increasingly they must enable child participation through their rights-based approaches, children's participation in concerned policy spaces and child centered risk communication (Munawar et al., 2003).

Natural hazards are not occasional phenomena with unfortunate consequences. Floods, wind and storms, earthquakes, drought, volcanic eruption, and tsunamis lead to about 400 national disasters, an average of 74,000 deaths and more than 230 million people affected every single year (CRED, 2008).

The agencies forming the children in a Changing Climate Coalition (CCC) recognized that the immediate and greater steps must be taken to reduce the risks to children from the horrifying disasters (Tanner et al., 2009).

Ernakulam was among the most affected districts over past three-four days. Aluva, Paravur and Eloor witnessed large-scale evacuations as they got submerged under water. However, these areas in Ernakulam are looking at normalcy as the water level is receding due to some respite from heavy rains over the past couple of days (the week, 2018)

Methodology

Both primary data and secondary data were used. Primary data are collected by surveying the parents in the study area, teachers and the public with the help of a questionnaire and interview and secondary sources includes books, magazines, newspapers and journals. The study area includes Aluva and paravur in Ernakulam district. The data collected are analysed and various findings and conclusions are drawn.

Major findings

Effect of flood on Education

- Emotional stress among children was on a rise as many children had to stay at home worried to keep their life safe and other children at camps found it difficult to get engaged to reduce vulnerability.
- The schools which were functioning as relief centre were completely spoiled and the furniture were damaged by the refugees.
- In order to cover the portions, the quality of education had to be compromised.

Mitigation measures that were used by the schools during floods

- Schools were opened as relief camps and a centre to provide necessities to the flood affected people
- Many schools were opened as emergency call centres and public was mobilised to form rescue teams
- Vehicles (Bus) were used to help evacuate the affected people
- Free counselling was given to students to help them recover from emotional stress
- Waste management measures were undertaken by the faculties of certain schools

Limitation of the study

- Sample size may not be exact representative of the universe. There is possibility of some error to a limited extent.
- Since people have personal bias, chances of minute error cannot be ignored.

Conclusion

Kerala saw the worst case of flood in August 2018 and the impact of flood on the lives of people was at its worst. Almost all sectors had to face the consequence especially the education sector where the mental, emotional and psychological aspects of children were at the question. Schools along with the support of government played an active part in taking mitigating measures against flood and that could be considered as a relief to the affected people. It would be appreciable if the measures to be taken during any disaster could be included in the curriculum and frequent mock drills be given to students and locals.

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